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Merging Realities: A Systematic Review on the Impact of Augmented Reality and Robot-Assisted Surgery for Trauma Management

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Abstract

Introduction: Trauma remains a leading cause of mortality worldwide, requiring rapid, precise surgical intervention. Robotic-assisted surgery offers enhanced dexterity and accuracy, while augmented reality (AR) enables real-time anatomical visualization, aiding complex decision-making. The integration of these technologies in trauma care is an emerging frontier, with the potential to improve outcomes in high-stakes scenarios. However, their use in emergency settings is still limited and underexplored. This systematic review evaluates current evidence on the combined use of AR and robotic-assisted surgery in trauma care, highlighting clinical outcomes, implementation feasibility, and existing challenges to guide future research and clinical adoption.

Methodology: This review was conducted in accordance with PRISMA guidelines. A comprehensive search was performed across PubMed, Scopus, and Google Scholar for studies published from January 2010 to May 2025, using combinations of terms related to “augmented reality”, “extended reality”, “robotic surgery”, “emergency care” and “trauma.” Titles, abstracts, and full texts were screened independently by the reviewer.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Studies involving human subjects undergoing trauma surgery with the assistance of AR and/or robot systems.
2. Articles published in English.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Studies focusing solely on elective surgeries without a trauma component.
2. Non-peer-reviewed articles, editorials, and conference abstracts.

Results: Forty-one studies met the inclusion criteria, covering robotic-assisted and AR-guided procedures in Neurology 2 (4.88%), Thoracic 3 (7.32%), Emergency 10 (24.39%), Orthopedic 12 (29.27%), and Abdominal 14 (34.15%). Sixteen were AR/XR focused, and twenty-two examined robotic surgery.

Reported benefits of robotic surgery included reduced operative time, blood loss, postoperative complications, and lower conversion to open surgery in approximately 1,067,263 cases according to one study. Lesser nerve injury (212 patients). In other trials, it showed similar complication rates to Laparoscopy in 1063 patients, with longer operative times in some complex procedures but reduced patient and shorter hospitalizations, suggesting improved postoperative experience. However, costs were significantly higher. Multiple papers noted the need for large-scale studies to determine the efficacy and cost-effectiveness.

Augmented Reality elevated accuracy in fracture fixation and arthroscopic trauma interventions. Seven studies demonstrate improved anatomical visualization and more precise intraoperative guidance for various surgical procedures. AR-based rehabilitation was linked to better pain management and functional outcomes over traditional methods in numerous researches. Simulation-based training with augmented reality and robotic systems remains the gold standard, it dramatically enhances trauma surgeons' technical skills, decision-making, and overall procedural confidence.

Barriers to clinical adoption included high costs, a steep learning curve, set-up time, triage, and limited utility in unstable/polytrauma patients requiring immediate intervention. Technical limitations, such as AR lag and robotic responsiveness in dynamic trauma scenarios, were also noted. The combined use of AR and robotics is mostly limited to small-scale studies and simulations.

Despite early evidence supporting patient outcomes and safety, large-scale real-world data on combined AR-robotic approaches in trauma care are lacking. Further research should focus on clinical trials, protocol development, and economic feasibility to establish their role in acute trauma surgery.

Conclusion: This systematic review highlights the emerging role of Robot-Assisted Surgery and Augmented Reality in enhancing trauma care. Robotic systems offer superior precision, reduced complications, and improved recovery metrics, while AR strengthens intraoperative visualization, supports advanced training and rehabilitation. Despite said benefits, real-world application remains limited by cost, technical complexity, and logistical challenges in unstable

trauma cases. The combined use of these technologies shows promise but is currently supported by limited-scale studies. Future effort must focus on high-volume clinical trials, cost-benefit analyses, and development of standardized, trauma/emergency-specific implementation protocols for different surgical procedures.

Figures

PRISMA flowchart